

CYANOBACTERIA ASSESSMENT IN ITALIAN AND SWEDISH WATERS FROM SPACE

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Summary

Earth Observation (EO) is a cost-effective tool for obtaining spatial information on the water quality status and processes taking place in seas and lakes. In particular, recent and expected advances in EO technology broaden the perspectives of monitoring toward the identification and quantification of plankton groups including cyanobacteria. The capability to detect cyanobacteria bloom is important because they can develop toxins hence presenting a range of amenity, water quality and treatment problems, as well as hazards to human health and ecological equilibrium. The problem is especially acute in the Baltic Sea where cyanobacterial blooms occur every summer covering areas of more than 100.000 km² and washing upon beaches during the summer holiday season. With respect to lakes, they frequently exhibit cyanobacterial blooms, with an increasing occurrence presumably in correlation with eutrophication and climate change, which has resulted in economic loss and considerable public interest in this phenomenon.

In such a frame, CYAN IS-WAS, aims to develop regional algorithms for detecting cyanobacterial blooms from both satellite and airborne data, and thence use those algorithms for mapping cyanobacteria during time, and thence try to derive the main environmental/ecological variables which cause the development of cyanobacteria. The cooperation activities are carried out by sharing EO data, methods and by performing joint field campaigns. The project involves training of PhD and MSc students of both countries for giving them experience in EO data analysis. The project is divulgated throughout a series of events, including scientific symposium/workshop and with scientific publications in ISI journals.

The exploitation of EO data allowed us to identify the occurrence, blooming, persistence and degradation of cyanobacteria communities in selected Swedish and Italian aquatic ecosystems. The main scientific findings are:

- an extremely high variability in cyanobacteria optical properties was found, thus enhancing the great importance of tuning the EO based algorithms depending on study area features;
- hyperspectral images, appropriately corrected, calibrated and validated, enabled the mapping of cyanobacteria blooms; some advantage of using radar data was also demonstrated for mapping abundant blooms in presence of clouds;
- comparative studies on marine (Baltic vs. north Adriatic) and freshwater (Vänern vs. subalpine deep lakes, Trasimeno and Mantova) have been accomplished thanks to joint field campaign and satellite images analysis;
- Nitrogen limitation in summer in the Baltic Sea proper is a decisive factor contributing to the development of blooms of filamentous cyanobacteria occurring during summer; EO work in the NW Baltic Sea has shown that we can derive chlorophyll concentrations in Baltic Sea coastal waters reliably from MERIS data (Hervey *et al.* 2013);
- the amount of suspended solids transported by Po river (but also by other secondary rivers as Adige and Tagliamento) into the north Adriatic Sea, reduces the available light that can be used by phytoplankton component hence also hindering the growth of cyanobacteria;

- the ratio between water surface and water volume is a key factor in the regulation of cyanobacteria dynamics in lakes and lagoons while biogeochemical analysis suggested that a series of cascade reactions (limited aeration, anoxia, chemical reduction, phosphorus release) can determine alterations in stoichiometric ratios of principal nutrients (N and P), which have a decisive role in the generation and intensity of cyanobacteria blooms.

With respect to cooperation activities the results are the following: 5 joint campaigns have been carried out (Mantova and Vänern lakes; Baltic and Adriatic seas); 7 joint workshops were attended by project partners; 14 papers in ISI journals plus a series of papers in conference proceedings have been published; 1 PhD and 4 MSc students have been graduated thanks to the project.

1 Project's aims

The objective of the cyan-IS-was project was the understanding of cyanobacteria bloom dynamics inside lacustrine and coastal aquatic environments through remote sensing techniques.

In particular, research activities were finalized to the definition of semi-empirical algorithms, based on in situ measures, able to derive descriptive maps about cyanobacteria blooms from satellite images. These activities were focused in different aquatic environments representing Subalpine, Mediterranean and Boreal eco-regions, with distinct salinity, morphology and trophic characteristics, thus affected by different cyanobacteria dynamics and bloom occurring frequencies.

In the fourth year of activity the scientific research is oriented towards the new generation of satellites while the divulgation activities were focused on the strength of the cooperation between Italy and Sweden. The work from Swedish coastal waters showed that remote sensing methods are reliable enough to support coastal management, and improve both temporal and spatial resolution of bloom dynamics [1, 2].

2 Project's team

The project team is composed by researchers, post-doc and PhD students, as well as by experts of the field.

Italian research unit

Name	Institute	Main role
Claudia Giardino	CNR-IREA, Milano	Italian PI
Mariano Bresciani	CNR-IREA, Milano	EO and ecology
Erica Matta	CNR-IREA, Milano	Fieldwork and EO
Simone Lella	CNR-IREA, Milano	EO and ICT
Daniela Stroppiana	CNR-IREA, Milano	Fieldwork and EO

Mauro Musanti	CNR-IREA, Milano	Fieldwork
Alba L' Astorina	CNR-IREA, Milano	Divulgation

Swedish research unit

Name	Institute	Main role
Susanne Kratzer	Stockholm University	Swedish PI
Niklas Strömbeck	Strömbeck Consulting	Project manager, optics and ecology
Therese Harvey	Stockholm University	Bio-optics and fieldwork activities and remote sensing analysis
Jose Beltran	Stockholm University	EO and fieldwork; evaluation of algorithms

In particular for each year the project is worth of the specialized team.

Cyan-IS-Was was based on the collaboration between the CNR-IREA in Milan and the University of Stockholm, which over the years of the project have shared activities of measures in situ, processing of satellite data and ecological analysis. In order to respond to the aims of the project, other research Italian and Swedish bodies were involved in various activities. For instance, in situ measurement were carried out with the technical and scientific collaboration of the CNR-ISMAR of Venice and of the LUODE consulting in Stockholm; processing data from Earth Observation (EO) implied the participation of the CNR-ISSIA researchers of Bari and of the Brockman Geomatics Sweden, while for ecological analysis Cyan-IS-was partners collaborated with the University of Parma and the CNR-ISE of Pallanza and Klaipėda University Coastal Research and Planning Institute. Stockholm University has been strongly cooperating with Bio-Optika, UK, which supported the CyanIsWas field work in lake Vänern.

3 Introduction

The Earth, observed from Space, appears as a "Blue Planet", given the abundant and unusual presence of water. Water has allowed the development of a surprising number of life forms and it is essential for nearly the totality of living beings. However 97% of water resources consists of salty waters (oceans and seas), while 2% is made of fresh water trapped in glaciers and polar caps. Only 1% of the water coming from lakes, rivers and ground water remains available for human needs, even though the accessibility is not everywhere uniform on Earth [3].

Strategic and sustainable water management is needed also considering the estimates provided by the World Water Development Report [4] suggesting a decrease in the amount of water availability of 30% per capita in the next twenty years. In order to support sustainable management of water resources the European Community adopted a Water Framework Directive (WFD) [5] introducing new approaches for protection of aquatic ecosystems (lakes, rivers, swamps, springs, coastal waters etc.). For achieving this goal WFD requires local authorities to classify their water bodies and analyze their ecological status according to three different aspects: physical-chemical characteristics of water, structure of biological communities and anthropogenic factors affecting the basin as all these variables are crucial to protect the ecosystem. Describing the relationship between both abiotic and biotic components and anthropogenic determinants is of primary importance since the breaking of the natural equilibrium has often dramatic effects on the environment. Among problems related to alteration of the balance in aquatic ecosystems, eutrophication, that is an excessive development of phytoplankton component in water, is causing major alarms for the protection of water quality of lakes and coastal ecosystems[6]. Eutrophication is caused by natural and/or human-driven factors which impact environmental conditions and constitute a problem for the treatment of water for human consumption (drinking water), as well as being a danger to public health, given the occasional toxicity of some of its components when coming into contact with humans during recreational activities [7]. For instance cyanobacteria, a group of phytoplankton, can reach extremely high concentrations under favorable conditions, thus being able to dominate over other phytoplanktonic groups and leading to the formation of the so-called Harmful Algal Blooms (HAB). HAB are main indicators of eutrophication and their potential toxic effect is given by the fact that some cyanobacteria species can produce different types of toxins which are harmful to humans and animals. Many epidemiological ongoing projects try to understand which levels and

factors specifically can determine the toxicity of cyanobacteria blooms, requiring more data on their exact concentration and distribution at the time of sampling [8]. In the Baltic Sea, filamentous cyanobacteria are highly competitive during nitrogen limitation in summer because of their capability of fixing nitrogen.

Fig. 1. Some environmental effects due to cyanobacteria blooms occurrence in aquatic ecosystem.

The knowledge on the phenomenon of bloom development is quite impressive: more than 34000 scientific articles [9] have been published in research fields like microbiology, molecular biology and genetics. However many gaps still remain about data, such as distribution and proliferation of cyanobacteria, that could be useful to draw up plans for monitoring and prevention of linked risk. Limited understanding is also due to technical-operational issues linked to different classification and methods of counting, to lack of standardization in sampling frequency and counting. More knowledge is then necessary for setting up a useful framework for determining the risk of public exposure [7].

Conventional monitoring means, based on infrequent ship sampling at a few fixed monitoring stations, have many drawbacks such as their high costs and since the extremely variable character of cyanobacteria blooms - which are strongly associated with either seasonal variations and temperature or availability of organic substances and nutrients - can't be easily deduced [7]. Harvey et al. [2] showed that conventional monitoring by ship also misses out bloom development that was observed by satellite as ship sampling is often not frequent enough. In order to provide all necessary information for ecological analysis, stealing valuable tools for monitoring and follow extension and changes in cyanobacteria distribution become necessary. For over twenty years Remote Sensing technology has been a powerful tool to integrate usual limnological and oceanographic data in a temporal and spatial analysis of some parameters of water quality. In particular, Remote Sensing allows to obtain information about the processes of diffusion and absorption of the electromagnetic energy in aquatic environment.

Keywords (ISI-WoS):Remote sensing+chlorophyll+lakes
 Categorie Remote Sensing, Marine Freshwater Biology

Fig. 2. Publications about cyanobacteria blooms and Remote Sensing means. A growing number of studies have appeared during the last twenty years.

Traditionally mapping chlorophyll-a concentration is fundamental for studying water quality; however, the rather recent capability to obtain information on the time-space distribution of cyanobacteria blooms through product-maps by Remote Sensing techniques is more innovative and useful. Moreover, Remote Sensing allows a systematic comparison among the various worldwide cases of algal blooms; this makes this methodology more interesting considering that the frequency of such phenomenon has been documented in several parts of the world since 1970 and is still growing.

Massive blooms of cyanobacteria are known and reported in different lakes and lagoon over the world: Okarito lagoon (New Zealand), Curonian Lagoon (Lituania-Russia) and Patos Lagoong (Brazil), Aland Lake (Finland), St. George Lake (Switzerland) and Orielson Lake (Australia). The most affected coastal areas are the Baltic Sea and American coastal areas.

Fig. 3. Left: Detecting map about eutrophication events along Mediterranean regions due to different planktonic species. Right: Occurrence of eutrophication events along United States coastal environments.

In Europe cyanobacteria affect basins among different nations including Italy, where according to data provided by the National Institute of Health cyanobacteria blooms concern a total of 50 sites of water between lakes and ponds.

Fig. 4. Detected cyanobacteria species along several Italian sites (Istituto Superiore Sanità, Italy).

The monitoring of the phenomenon has grown among local stakeholders and health authorities due to cases of poisoning of animals, including man [7]. Also Scandinavian peninsula is strongly involved in the same emergence management given a large surface occupied by lakes, which are estimated 100,000 just in Sweden, many of them being rather wide, and due to the presence of cyanobacteria blooms in Baltic Sea [7]. In this context traditional sampling-based methodologies constitute a limited and extremely time-consuming approach while satellite methodologies are particularly appropriate providing the spatial and temporal coverage needed and giving the opportunity to examine resemblances and differences between Mediterranean and Sub-Nordic regions. This also enables an integrated vision of the problem and a collaborative approach.

A positive example of collaboration between different research teams facing with this environmental problem is the project Cyan-IS-Was (Cyanobacteria Assessment in Italian and Swedish Waters from space) supported by the Italian Republic and the Kingdom of Sweden within the Agreement on Cultural Cooperation, Education, Science and Technology emphasizing the role of science and technology in the economic, social and cultural development of both countries. Cyan-IS-Was involves Italian and Swedish partners approaching the problem with complementary

skills, data and methodologies given the common aim to produce advanced knowledge for the aquatic ecosystems management.

The Cyan-IS-Was project has two aims:

- to understand the dynamics of cyanobacteria blooms in aquatic environments as lake and coastal waters through Remote Sensing techniques. In particular research activities aim:
 - to develop algorithms able to turn satellite images - Earth Observation (EO) data - into descriptive maps useful to discriminate the presence and concentrations of cyanobacteria in waters;
 - to integrate EO data with in situ measurement and climate weather data, in order to get information useful to the management of cyanobacteria blooms from the relevant competent authority;
- to develop cooperative activities between Italian and Swedish partners, through different systems such as joint campaigns, workshops, dissemination of results and scientific education activities, in order to facilitate sharing of knowledge and an accelerated understanding of the phenomenon that regards both the countries involved.

4 Research activities

In this paragraph we illustrate the main activities developed in 2013.

4.1 Analysis of the possibilities of using new generation hyperspectral sensors for mapping cyanobacteria

The capability of retrieving water quality parameters, such as chlorophyll-a (Chl-a), with ocean colour satellites (e.g. MERIS, MODIS, SeaWiFS) has been widely established and published during the last decade. Several studies have demonstrated the capability of optical remote sensing for mapping algal blooms in marine, lacustrine and lagoon environments, and various approaches have been successfully applied.

However, Earth Observation monitoring efforts today are driven by ocean colour satellites with rather low spatial resolution and medium spectral resolution or by commercial sensors much expensive. Moreover, unfortunately, the end of the Envisat mission (2012) will not consent to go further into these applications by using data gathered from MERIS.

Few new satellites (e.g. Sentinel-2, Sentinel-3, EnMAP, PRISMA) will be launched in the near future which will provide a wealth of new data at increased spatial, spectral and temporal resolution, and recently new satellites have been launched (e.g. LANDSAT-8, HICO).

The availability of new satellite sensors is due to the excellent results obtained from the application of remote sensing techniques for environmental analysis and are framed within a global system of observations among which we must mention Copernicus, the new European observation system for monitoring the Earth based on remote sensing data.

Copernicus consists of a complex set of systems which collect data from multiple sources: earth observation satellites and in situ sensors such as ground stations, airborne and sea-borne sensors. Copernicus will be operational and will process these data and provide users with reliable and up-to-date information through a set of services related to environmental and security issues.

The services address six thematic areas: land, marine, atmosphere, climate change, emergency management and security. They support a wide range of applications, including environment protection, management of urban areas, regional and local planning, agriculture, forestry, fisheries, health, transport, climate change, sustainable development, civil protection and tourism. The main users of Copernicus services are policy makers and public authorities who need the information to develop environmental legislation and policies or to take critical decisions in the event of an emergency, such as a natural disaster or a humanitarian crisis.

The community engagement is enshrined in the European program Horizon 2020, this is the financial instrument implementing the Innovation Union, a Europe 2020 flagship initiative aimed at securing Europe's global competitiveness. Running from 2014 to 2020 with a budget of just over €70 billion¹, the EU's new Programme for research and innovation is part of the drive to create new growth and jobs in Europe. Horizon 2020 provides major simplification through a single set of rules. It will combine all research and innovation funding currently provided through the EU Framework Programmes for Research and Technical Development, the innovation related activities

of the Competitiveness and Innovation Framework Programme (CIP) and the European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT). Horizon 2020 will tackle societal challenges by helping to bridge the gap between research and the market by, for example, helping innovative enterprise to develop technological innovations into viable products with real commercial potential. This market-driven approach will include creating partnerships with the private sector and EU Member States to bring together the resources needed. International cooperation will be an important cross-cutting priority of Horizon 2020. In addition to Horizon 2020 being fully open to international participation, targeted actions with key partner countries and regions will focus on the EU's strategic priorities. Through a new strategy, a strategic and coherent approach to international cooperation will be ensured across Horizon 2020.

The opportunity to have new images with high spatial, radiometric and temporal resolution, for the study of cyanobacteria blooms is of great significance for the study of their dynamics and to provide useful data for environmental management.

The launch date of the new sensors is approaching and one should be prepared to take full advantage of these new data sources from the start.

In the coming years several optical Earth Observation satellites will be launched and others sensors are newly available, which will provide new opportunities for inland water monitoring:

- **SENTINEL-2 (ESA):** The pair of Sentinel-2 satellites will routinely deliver high-resolution optical images globally, providing enhanced continuity of SPOT- and Landsat-type data. Sentinel-2 will provide multispectral images with 13 spectral bands between 443 nm and 2190 nm with a spectral resolution between 15 nm and 180 nm and a spatial resolution of 10 m, 20 m and 60 m. At mid-latitudes the revisit time will be 2- 3 days with a swath width of 290 km. The 13 spectral bands guarantee consistent time series, showing variability in land surface conditions and minimizing any artefacts introduced by atmospheric variability. The increased swath width along with the short revisit time allows rapid changes to be monitored, such as vegetation during the growing season. In essence, Sentinel-2 combines a large swath, frequent revisit, and systematic acquisition of all land surfaces at high-spatial resolution and with a large number of spectral bands, all of which makes a unique mission to serve Copernicus. Data from Sentinel-2 will benefit services associated with, for example, land management by European and national institutes, the agricultural industry and forestry, as well as disaster control and humanitarian relief operations (including cyanobacteria blooms).
- **SENTINEL-3 (ESA):** The Sentinel-3 mission's main objective is to measure sea-surface topography, sea- and land-surface temperature and ocean- and land-surface colour with high-end accuracy and reliability in support of ocean forecasting systems, and for environmental and climate monitoring. Sentinel-3 builds directly on a proven heritage pioneered by ERS-2 and Envisat. Its innovative instrument package includes:
 - A Sea and Land Surface Temperature Radiometer (SLSTR), which is based on Envisat's Advanced Along Track Scanning Radiometer (AATSR), to determine global sea-surface temperatures to an accuracy of 0.1 K.
 - The Ocean and Land Colour Instrument (OLCI) is based on heritage from Envisat's Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MERIS). With 21 bands,

compared to the 15 on MERIS, a design optimized to minimize sun-glint and, a resolution of 300 m over all surfaces, OLCI marks a new generation of measurements over ocean and land. The swath of OLCI and nadir SLSTR fully overlap.

- A dual-frequency (Ku and C band) advanced Synthetic Aperture Radar Altimeter (SRAL) is based CryoSat heritage and provides measurements at a resolution of ~300m in SAR mode along track. SRAL is supported by a microwave radiometer for atmospheric correction and a DORIS receiver for orbit positioning.
- OLCI will have 21 spectral bands compared to 15 for MERIS, with amongst other one band at the end of the UV (400 nm) and the beginning of the SWIR (1020 nm). As a continuation of MERIS Sentinel-3 will provide a wealth of data for the ocean colour community. Despite the low spatial resolution, the high revisit time and the well chosen new spectral bands at 400 nm and 1020 nm provide opportunities for improved yellow matter retrievals, atmospheric correction, and even TSM retrievals in very turbid estuaries

The pair of Sentinel-3 satellites will enable a short revisit time of less than two days for OLCI and less than one day for SLSTR at the equator. The satellite orbit provides a 27-day repeat for the topography package, with a 4-day sub-cycle. The remote sensing group at Stockholm University has been active member of the MERIS validation team since 2001, and since the beginning of 2012 is also leading the Swedish Sentinel-3 validation team (in cooperation with Strömbeck Consulting and Brockmann Geomatic AB).

Near-realtime data will be provided for ocean forecasting, sea-ice charting, and maritime safety services needing accurate and timely measurements of the state of the ocean surface, including surface temperature, ocean ecosystems, water quality and pollution monitoring.

- PRISMA (ASI): (PRecursores IperSpettrale of the application mission) is an Italian Space Agency earth observation system with innovative electro-optical instrumentation which combines a hyperspectral sensor with a panchromatic, medium-resolution camera. The advantages of this combination are that in addition to the classical capability of observation based on the recognition of the geometrical characteristics of the scene, there is the one offered by hyperspectral sensors which can determine the chemical-physical composition of objects present on the scene. This offers the scientific community and users many applications in the field of environmental monitoring, resource management, crop classification, pollution control, etc. Further applications are possible even in the field of National Security. PRISMA satellite combines a hyperspectral sensor (designed to acquire data in the 400-2500 nm range, at a spectral resolution of 10 nm and at 30 m spatial resolution) with a high-resolution panchromatic camera (5 m). This combination provides bio-geo-physical parameters through hyperspectral data, adding the capability of recognizing geometric characteristics with high spatial resolution. In the VNIR range, the continuum of spectral bands permits to accurate reproduction of the in-situ spectra, improvement of the aquatic vegetation identifications and quantitative retrieval of water quality parameters. PRISMA is a "small" Italian mission of demonstrative/technological and

pre-operational nature. The fundamental objectives, in line with the PASN 2006-2008, are the following:

- To develop a small mission entirely in Italy for monitoring natural resources and atmosphere characteristics, taking advantage of the prior developments carried out by ASI.
 - Make available in a short period of time the data necessary to the scientific community for developing new applications for environmental risk management and observation of the territory, based on high-resolution spectral images.
 - Test the hyperspectral payload in orbit - the first or among the first at the European level.
- **EnMAP:** The Environmental Mapping and Analysis Program (EnMAP) is a German hyperspectral satellite mission that aims at monitoring and characterising the Earth's environment on a global scale. EnMAP serves to measure and model key dynamic processes of the Earth's ecosystems by extracting geochemical, biochemical and biophysical parameters, which provide information on the status and evolution of various terrestrial and aquatic ecosystems. The German hyperspectral EnMAP provide hyperspectral data (> 200 bands) in the 420-2450 nm range at a spatial resolution of 30 m. With off-nadir pointing, a revisit time of 4 days can be achieved. The almost continuous spectrum, coupled with a relatively high spatial resolution and revisit time of 4 days, offers the opportunity to derive new and essential products such as phytoplankton functional types (PFT). This information would be extremely valuable for the calibration of multi-species phytoplankton models. The primary mission objectives are:
 - to provide high-quality calibrated hyperspectral data for advanced remote sensing analyses;
 - to foster and develop novel methodologies that improve the accuracy of currently available remote sensing information and to provide advanced science-driven information products;
 - to obtain diagnostic geochemical, biochemical and biophysical parameters that describe the status and dynamics of various ecosystems to improve our understanding of complex environmental processes;
 - to provide information products that can serve as input for advanced ecosystem models;
 - to significantly contribute to environmental research studies, particularly in the fields of ecosystem functions, natural resource management, natural hazards and Earth system modelling; and
 - to develop new concepts and techniques for data extraction and assimilation to achieve synergies with other sensors.
 - **LANDSAT 8 (NASA):** is an American Earth observation satellite launched on February 11, 2013. It is the eighth satellite in the Landsat program, the satellite was built by Orbital Sciences Corporation, who served as prime contractor for the mission. Landsat 8 joins

Landsat 7 on-orbit, providing increased coverage of the Earth's surface. Providing moderate-resolution imagery, from 15 meters to 100 meters, of Earth's land surface and polar regions, Landsat 8 will operate in the visible, near-infrared, short wave infrared, and thermal infrared spectrums. Landsat 8 will capture approximately 400 scenes a day, an increase from the 250 scenes a day on Landsat 7. The OLI and TIRS sensors will see improved signal to noise (SNR) radiometric performance, enabling 12-bit quantization of data allowing for more bits for better land-cover characterization. The OLI instrument uses a push-broom sensor instead of whiskbroom sensors that were utilized on earlier Landsat satellites. The push-broom sensor aligns the imaging detector arrays along Landsat 8's focal plane allowing it to view across the entire swath, 115 miles (185 kilometers) cross-track field of view, as opposed to sweeping across the field of view. With over 7,000 detectors per spectral band, the push-broom design results in increased sensitivity, fewer moving parts, and improved land surface information. OLI collects data from nine spectral bands. Seven of the nine bands are consistent with the Thematic Mapper (TM) and Enhanced Thematic Mapper Plus (ETM+) sensors found on earlier Landsat satellites, providing for compatibility with the historical Landsat data, while also improving measurement capabilities. Two new spectral bands, a deep blue coastal / aerosol band and a shortwave-infrared cirrus band, will be collected, allowing scientists to measure water quality and improve detection of high, thin clouds.

- HICO: The Hyperspectral Imager for the Coastal Ocean (HICOTM) is an imaging spectrometer based on the PHILLS airborne imaging spectrometers. HICO is the first spaceborne imaging spectrometer designed to sample the coastal ocean. HICO samples selected coastal regions at 90 m with full spectral coverage (380 to 960 nm sampled at 5.7 nm) and a very high signal-to-noise ratio to resolve the complexity of the coastal ocean. HICO demonstrates coastal products including water clarity, bottom types, bathymetry and on-shore vegetation maps. Each year HICO collects approximately 2000 scenes from around the world. The current focus is on providing HICO data for scientific research on coastal zones and other regions around the world. To that end we have developed this website and we will make data available to registered HICO Data Users who wish to work with us as a team to exploit these data. For the first three years, HICO was sponsored by the Office of Naval Research as an Innovative Naval Prototype (INP); support is now provided by NASA's International Space Station (ISS) Program.

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The research activities carried out in relation to new sensors available and future sensors has been to re-sample the spectral signatures acquired in situ with the radiometric characteristics of the sensors mentioned above. Resampled to the spectral signatures have been applied to different algorithms bibliography in order to assess the ability to discriminate and map the blooms of cyanobacteria.

Figures 5, 6 and 7 show how the new generation sensors we radiometric characteristics that increase the ability to discriminate the spectral characteristics of cyanobacteria.

If we add the higher spatial resolution and times of acquisition ever more efficient, is easy to understand how, in the future the use of satellite images allow detailed study of the blooms of cyanobacteria in aquatic environments.

Fig. 5. Water reflectance spectra measured in Lake Maggiore in the last ten years (in bold, the mean value). At the bottom, the spectra are plotted at the same spectral resolution of the instruments (i.e., ASD and WISP-3) used to collect them. In the panel above the mean spectra has been resampled according to spectral resolution of most common sensors used to assess water quality of lakes from space [10].

Fig. 6. Water reflectance spectra measured in laboratory in a sample of cyanobacteria (*Mycrocystis* sp.).

Fig. 7. Indications on the bands of the PRISMA sensor can be used for the mapping of photosynthetic pigments contained in cyanobacteria: phycocyanin (PC), phycoerythrin (PR), Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) and the phenomena of surface scum.

4.2 Mapping cyanobacteria bloom from recent satellite data

Below are two examples of applications of the new sensors LANDSAT-8 and HICO for the study of the phenomena of growth and blooms of cyanobacteria in south Alpine Italian lakes.

At first of August, 2013, in Lake Como occurred an intense bloom of *Dolichospermum lemmermannii* (Fig. 8), the monitoring carried out by ARPA Lombardia (Lecco Department) has regard to the analysis of phytoplankton, the density of *Dolichospermum lemmermannii* was equal to 365 million cells/liter, for a total biovolume and chlorophyll a respectively of 120,2 mm³l⁻¹ e 141 µgl⁻¹.

Fig. 8. Surface blooms of *Dolichospermum lemmermannii* registered in Dervio (Lake Como) on 02/08/13.

ARPA has concluded the report of the monitoring with the sentence: "For the characterization of both spatial and temporal phenomena of flowering should be an intensification of monitoring in the period when weather conditions become favorable and the use of modeling techniques and remote sensing".

For this reason, were analyzed LANDSAT-8 before and after the period specified by ARPA (July 16 to 25, 10/17/01 August) and it was found that the phenomenon of flowering it was found only in the date of 01 August to evidence the speed and variability of growth of cyanobacteria.

Figures 9 and 10 shows the maps obtained from the Landsat-8 on 01 August when we highlight the abundance of the phenomenon occurred, and the identification of the spatial presence of surface accumulation of cyanobacteria.

Fig. 9. Qualitative maps of phytoplankton surface concentration estimated by Landsat-8 on 01/08/2013.

Fig. 10. In purple, areas with surface aggregations of cyanobacteria estimated by Landsat-8 on 01/08/2013.

Always on the recommendation of local agencies (ARPA Veneto), in the summer of 2012, in the coastal areas to the south of Lake Garda occurred blooms of the cyanobacteria *Anabaena* sp surface. We acquired and processed images of the HICO sensor, and the image of 29 June 2012, nearly synchronous to the findings made in situ by ARPA (28 June 2012) the following was observed (Fig. 11) as stations with a greater amount of cyanobacteria the spectral signature HICO highlight the features characteristic of cyanobacteria (increased reflectance in the region between 640 and 650 nm).

Fig. 11. In the left the study area, in the right the graph with spectral signature from HICO in three different station characterized by different cyanobacteria quantitative.

4.3 Remote sensing technique for support coastal management: Swedish case study

The work from Swedish coastal waters showed that remote sensing methods are reliable enough to support coastal management, and improve both temporal and spatial resolution of bloom dynamics [1, 2].

In the Fig. 11 and 12, we showed some results of the Ocean color remote sensing can significantly improve levels of understanding of coastal ecosystems.

Fig. 12. Cyanobacteria bloom in the north-western Baltic Sea: MERIS K_a (490) image from 28 July 2008 (300 m resolution); MERIS K_a (490) algorithm [from 2]. The image was read into Google Earth. MERIS data by courtesy of the European Space Agency. Processing: Christian Vinterhav. [1].

Fig. 13. The use of remote sensing as diagnostic tool for eutrophication. [1]

5 Cooperation activities

A collaborative research environment, where sharing is encouraged, may be considered as an economic and suitable approach able to achieve high quality results. Sharing helps to decrease the chance that several researchers will develop the same studies in parallel or unknowingly perform the same experiment. That, in turn, reduces the costs of the research in terms of the funding and effort required [11].

Rapid and pervasive technological changes have facilitated the sharing of knowledge, creating new ways of acquiring, storing, manipulating and transmitting vast data volumes, as well as stimulating new habits of communication and collaboration among scientists [12]. Since new communication networks appeared, practice of sharing have become fundamental supporting the shift of social dynamics in research toward collaboration and open practices. Publishing scientific theories, including experimental and observational data, permits other to scrutinize them, to replicate experiments and to reuse data to create further understanding. It permits the identification of errors and for theories to be rejected or refined. It makes science a self-correcting process [13]. Therefore those emerging needs in many fields of science - as physics, genomics, remote sensing ecology - to share not only a theoretical knowledge but also various know-how at stake and skills, overcome the traditional autonomy of the scientists who worked individually and direct research in a way toward formation of international research teams. The Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) has recognized in a global system of research "a driving force and the agent of change" [14] adding that "the best strategies to find global responses to global problems are in the sharing of data and to provide international collaborations [12]".

The Cyan-IS-Was project referred to this framework not only promoting a collaborative research project for facing with a common environmental problem but also involving the governments of both countries in a bilateral agreement. The collaboration is in fact basis for almost all of the activities carried out within the project and has proved to be the determining factor to accelerate transfer of knowledge between the two groups of research and to reach a more complete understanding of the phenomenon. The collaborative approach of Cyan-IS-Was, as previously described, affected different traditional aspects of the project (methodology, use of instruments, multidisciplinary approach, outreach activities) as following:

- *methodological exchange* integrating laboratory measures and in situ measures;
- *instrumental intercomparison* of measurement techniques and experimental approach;
- *multidisciplinary approach* involving different skills and know-how of partners;
- *dissemination activities* sharing initiatives such as workshops and symposiums;
- *educational activities* involving PhD and MSc students.

These aspects supported project's results, stimulating value-adding processes that increased access to knowledge resources produced by partners [15]. Collaboration framework created good practices to better transfer knowledge within the scientific community and to society.

5.1 Methodological exchange

As already shown, classical sampling-techniques seem inadequate and insufficient in detecting the distribution and proliferation of cyanobacteria while Remote Sensing reveals more appropriate for obtaining information about the processes of diffusion and absorption of the electromagnetic energy in aquatic environment. However available literature on cyanobacteria blooms stresses the complexity of their quantitative retrieval and monitoring also through satellite data. In fact, if the spatial extent of cyanobacteria blooms is relatively simple to map, the retrieval of concentration may be tricky, especially at low levels and when the blossom does not occur on the surface but rather a few meters of depth. In this case a collaborative approach helped filling the mutual gaps by introducing an exchange of *methodology* integrating the data obtained from both methods (remote sensing analysis on the one hand as well as laboratory analysis and *in situ* measurements) in a single analysis. This approach consisted in finding the best mathematical equation that relates the reflectance recorded by satellite and the pigment concentration parameter measured *in situ*. In order to describe this equation it was fundamental to design semi-empirical and semi-analytical algorithms based on high capacity database, developed by sharing analysis during the previous years and integrating them with those contextual to Cyan-IS-Was project. Collaboration thus helped obtaining a data volume suitable to the definition of algorithms, resulting in a more extended data set than the one each partner could individually produce.

The database is composed of more than 300 electromagnetic spectra collected for lacustrine, marine and coastal environments. In order to achieve the goal different joint campaigns in lacustrine environments (e.g. Mantova Lakes, Italy and Lake Vänern, Sweden), lagoon environments (e.g., Venice Lagoon) and coastal marine areas (Adriatic Sea and Baltic Sea) measuring the optical properties of waters affected by cyanobacteria blooms were planned. *Methodology exchange* was therefore a fundamental step not only for achieving good scientific-technical objectives but also to exchange different expertise connected to procedures, processes and protocol of a campaign, thus building a *community of practice*.

The *community of practice* [16] is defined as a group of people who share a topic relative to a particular field and has the goal to accumulate knowledge about that issue through a know-how sharing. The concept was developed within "knowledge management" theory which isolated those experiences and those settings considered necessary to make the professional know-how of experts "explicit" and accessible to all. Through those systems the know-how becomes heritage for all the team members allowing the free acquisition of new knowledge from the participants. The knowledge-management has led to a wide series of processes for exchanging know-how and among these the community of practice is considered a resource often strategic within an organization. Joint campaigns, as properly defined as community of practice, appear therefore an opportunity not only to reach scientific results, but also to share know-how and to provide hands-on training for PhD students and other young professionals.

5.2 Instrumental intercomparison

Partner confronted one-another a lot with different types of measuring instruments used in some procedures and during different experimental set-ups. This instrumental intercomparison represented an important opportunity for a technical-scientific enrichment of all partners and gave interesting learning opportunities to PhD and MSc students involved in the project. In particular, four types of instrumental intercomparison were developed within the project:

- intercomparison of radiometers, multi-channel fluorometers and backscattering instruments: the use of different sensors in order to characterize the optical properties of the waters with and without cyanobacteria provided a framework for technical cooperation, which resulted in an opportunity for learning and improvement for all partners;
- intercomparison of images: the use of different sensors in order to obtain different images also was an occasion of *intercomparison* among partners; as a result of such a comparison a technical manual was drawn up which helped towards formalization and the capitalization of shared knowledge. This experience was then discussed and shared within two different workshops organized by the partner institutes in Stockholm and in Italy (Milan and Sirmione del Garda).

The activities of intercomparison also concerned the processing of satellite images as particular importance was given to atmospheric correction of the images. The partners compared different approaches based on the physics of the radiative transfer to remove the disturbance caused by atmospheric components in order to obtain images in reflectance as possible efficient and accurate for the study of the optical properties of waters.

5.3 Multidisciplinary approach

The *multidisciplinary approach* was a fundamental feature of the project since satellite analysis and limnological/oceanographic analysis complement each other. Cyan-IS-Was required specific and various skills which, in the context of a *community of practice*, can be found and easily shared between teams. Within the bilateral framework not only specific expertise, but also tools and technical skills for the correct use of the instruments were then at stake among partners. This was fundamental in the third year of the project, when through the collaboration of the Strömbeck Consulting the back-scattering data processing purchases from Hydrocat 6 (CNR-ISMAR OF) in the Adriatic Sea and the Baltic Sea were prepared. Strömbeck Consulting also participated in the workshop "Cyan-IS-Was project - Technical and Scientific discussion", Milan (Italy), 19-20 /07/2012, providing a contribution in their own field of activity. As many authors have underlined [20] the use of specialized know-how is an important element in multidisciplinary research: the technological advancement has produced a growing number of increasingly complex methodologies of investigation, requiring for each of them a specific competence. Since research tends to quickly absorb available technologies, the individual researcher is unable to cover all the skills required. When a team of researchers share expertise and products the total joint effort is capable of reaching the goals more quickly and with the best benefit. In those projects where partners assume the structure of the *learning organization* – that is work systems with the possibility to apply and quickly update the new knowledge available - specific skills are immediately transmitted and disseminated. Multidisciplinary here acts as a strong innovative element, in fact the ability to share different and supplementary perspectives when facing the same problem. As demonstrated by computational research on neuroscience [17], sharing experimental data allows researchers with different expertise to participate in the analysis of the same content using different approaches,

introducing not only useful perspectives and additional contributions, but also indicating different applications for the same product [18]. Research and knowledge evolution is not only the result of an increased access to data or resources, but also access to disciplines from various researchers [19]. Interdisciplinary groups in particular can bring many different and potentially complimentary epistemologies to bear on challenging and otherwise intractable questions [20]. In addition, the sharing of data and their treatment in a multidisciplinary dimension allows a rapid achievement of results. See the success of research programs such as the Human Genome Project or, in astronomy, the International Virtual Observatory Alliance [18].

5.4 Educational and dissemination activities

Government ministries and agencies in Europe make significant investments in research projects and programs to generate knowledge, tools and techniques necessary to underpin effective environmental policy-making and regulation. As explained in “Dissemination and implementation of environmental research”, a report published by Swedish Environmental Protection Agency, key steps in realizing the benefits from this investment are the dissemination of the research and its implementation in policy making and regulatory decision taking. In this context, one of the main goal of Cyan-IS-Was project consists in the dissemination of results not only within the research community but also to local authorities involved in water management. When research is to be used in policy-making and environmental management end-users should be involved also throughout the planning and execution stages to ensure the continuing coherence of the research questions and the answers that are needed. There is often a gap between end-users, owning local experience and data, and experts in various practices. These two actors speak sometimes different languages and look at themselves like as counterparts, thus exposing to risk results of their collaboration [22]. The Swedish team at Stockholm University have supported Brockmann Geomatic AB, Sweden, in building up an operational system for managers in close collaboration with end users [1]. The system can retrieve reliable quantitative information on the development of the spring bloom (diatoms and dinoflagellates) and cyanobacteria blooms in summer [2]. The system has been updated during 2013, and now also provides information on ecological status classification based on satellite data (www.vattenkvalitet.nu). This website is easily accessible, and also helps to disseminate recent research results to end-users and managers.

Furthermore, Cyan-IS-Was was divulged through a series of events, including scientific symposium/workshop and with scientific publications in ISI journals meeting paying attention to the end-users involvement all over the project. The end-users of the research (policy makers, regulatory decision takers etc.) could then closely interact with the researchers, contributing from the first steps of the project to the definition of the research questions, of research planning, carrying out dissemination and results. An important objective was to build mutual trust and relationships that could last also beyond the research project.

The project also gave an important accent to training activities and many PhD and MSc students from Italy and Sweden were taught on EO data analysis. The collaborative framework of Cyan-IS-Was project also provided an occasion to enhance learning processes. During the 20th century the concept of learning underwent important developments. Today the dominant concept is socio-constructivist in which learning is understood to be importantly shaped by the context in which it is situated and is actively constructed through social negotiation with others [23]. Redesigning learning environments is critical because of the significant changing taking place since the profound

transformation of “industrial” economy to “knowledge” economy. Knowledge is now the central driving force for economic activity and as knowledge has become so important then so has learning, in particular in such frameworks where sharing and transferring of knowledge is well promoted.

5.5 *Education*

Within the project young researchers and PhD/MSc students have been involved during 2013 in order to give them experience in remote sensing data analysis and measurements of water quality.

- Francesca Sanfilippo, MSc student in Environmental Sciences at University of Bologna, performed part of her educational activities on in situ data handling of Venice Lagoon within the scientific frame of cyan-IS-was project, and had previously been trained to measure bio-optical properties at Stockholm University.
- Riccardo Beltrandi, degree in Environmental Sciences in 2013, participated to the processing of HICO data in subalpine lake.

5.6 Scientific papers

International Journal with Peer Review

Paper #1

Recognizing harmful algal bloom based on remote sensing reflectance band ratio

Journal: *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing* 053556-1 Vol. 5, **2011**

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Abstract: We present a band ratio algorithm based on remote sensing reflectance (RRS) data to detect an algal bloom composed of cyanobacteria (*Planktothrix* spp.) and chrysophytes in Lake Idro, a small meso-eutrophic lake situated in the subalpine region (northern Italy). The bloom started around the first week of September 2010 and persisted for about 1 month, with highest mean chlorophyll-a concentrations (17.5 ± 1.6 mgm^{-3}) and phytoplankton cellular density ($7,250,000$ $\text{cell} \cdot \text{l}^{-1}$) measured on September 14, 2010. RRS data obtained from in situ measurements were first investigated to select the diagnostic wavelengths (i.e., 560 and 620 nm) of both phycoerythrin (present in the *Planktothrix* spp.) and other pigments (e.g., fucoxanthin, common to several species of chrysophyte). Testing the algorithm on RRS data derived from atmospherically corrected image data showed the ability of the medium resolution imaging spectrometer (MERIS) to detect the bloom also. The results demonstrate that a combination of in situ and MERIS data is a valuable tool to monitor the extent and duration of phytoplankton blooms.

Keywords: remote sensing reflectance; MERIS; harmful algal bloom; lake

Paper #2

Remote sensing supports the definition of the water quality status of Lake Omodeo (Italy)

Journal: *European Journal of Remote Sensing*, 45: 349-360, **2012**

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Abstract: Lake Omodeo is the largest artificial reservoir of Sardinia and its waters are a valuable resource for irrigation, domestic and industrial purposes. Lake Omodeo has serious problems of eutrophication. Since 2007 the local water authority has been undertaken a monitoring program designed to test an integrated methodology based on field measurements and remote sensing. This study illustrates the production of multitemporal spatialised maps of chlorophyll-a concentrations from satellite data acquired from Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MERIS). The analysis confirmed the eutrophic status of Omodeo, especially between spring and summer (mainly due to cyanobacteria bloom) assessing their dependency on weather conditions and river inputs.

Keywords: Chlorophyll-a, cyanobacteria, MERIS sensor, meteorological factors, trophic status.

Paper #3**BOMBER: A tool for estimating water quality and bottom properties from remote sensing images**

Journal: *Computers & Geosciences*, 45: 313 – 318, 2012

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Abstract: BOMBER (Bio-Optical Model Based tool for Estimating water quality and bottom properties from Remote sensing images) is a software package for simultaneous retrieval of the optical properties of water column and bottom from remotely sensed imagery, which makes use of bio-optical models for optically deep and optically shallow waters. Several menus allow the user to choose the model type, to specify the input and output files, and to set all of the variables involved in the model parameterization and inversion. The optimization technique allows the user to retrieve the maps of chlorophyll concentration, suspended particulate matter concentration, coloured dissolved organic matter absorption and, in case of shallow waters, bottom depth and distributions of up to three different types of substrate, defined by the user according to their albedo. The software requires input image data that must be atmospherically corrected to remote sensing reflectance values. For both deep and shallow water models, a map of the relative error involved in the inversion procedure is also given. The tool was originally intended to estimate water quality in lakes; however thanks to its general design, it can be applied to any other aquatic environments (e.g., coastal zones, estuaries, lagoons) for which remote sensing reflectance values are known. BOMBER is fully programmed in IDL (Interactive Data Language) and uses IDL widgets as graphical user interface. It runs as an add-on tool for the ENVI+IDL image processing software and is available on request.

Keywords: Remote sensing images; Water; Bio-optical modelling; Inversion

Highlights: - A software package simultaneously retrieves properties of water column and bottom from remotely sensed imagery. - The tool implements an optimization technique to invert a bio-optical model for deep and shallow waters. - The software is programmed in IDL and runs as an add-on tool for the image processing software the ENVI+IDL. - A series of GUIs allow the user to parameterize the bio-optical model and to run the inversion.

Paper #4**Intercomparison in the field between the new WISP-3 and other radiometers (TriOS Ramses, ASD FieldSpec, and TACCS)**

Journal: *Journal of Applied Remote Sensing*, 6, 063615-1 2012

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Abstract: Optical close-range instruments can be applied to derive water quality parameters for monitoring purposes and for validation of optical satellite data. In situ radiometers are often difficult to deploy, especially from a small boat or a remote location. The water insight spectrometer (WISP-3) is a new hand-held radiometer for monitoring water quality, which automatically performs measurements with three radiometers (Lsky, Lu, Ed) and does not need to be connected with cables and electrical power during measurements.

The instrument is described and its performance is assessed by an intercomparison to well-known radiometers, under real fieldwork conditions using a small boat and with sometimes windy and cloudy weather. Root mean squared percentage errors relative to those of the TriOS system were generally between 20% and 30% for remote sensing reflection, which was comparable to those of the other instruments included in this study. From this assessment, it can be stated that for the tested conditions, the WISP-3 can be used to obtain reflection spectra with accuracies in the same range as well-known instruments. When tuned with suitable regional algorithms, it can be used for quick scans for water quality monitoring of Chl, SPM, and aCDOM.

Keywords: WISP-3; radiometer; intercomparison; reflectance

Paper #5

Retrospective analysis of spatial and temporal variability of chlorophyll-a in the Curonian Lagoon

Journal: *Journal of Coastal Conservation*, DOI 10.1007/s11852-012-0192-5, **2012**

Authors: M. Bresciani¹, C. Giardino¹, D. Stroppiana¹, R. Pilkaitytė², M. Zilius², M. Bartoli³, A. Razinkovas²

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Abstract: The Curonian Lagoon, the largest in Europe (total surface area 1584 km²), is located in the southern part of the Baltic Sea, from which it is separated by a narrow sand bar and to which it is connected by the Klaipeda Straits. It is characterised by shallow eutrophic waters (mean depth 3.8 m) with average low salinity (<5‰) due to the nutrient-rich freshwaters discharged by the river Nemunas. Cyanobacteria blooms, including species producing toxic metabolites, have been a frequent phenomenon in summer. In this study a series of MERIS Full Resolution (FR) satellite images acquired between 2004 and 2009 during summer periods were used to assess the temporal evolution and spatial variability of the lagoon water quality in terms of chlorophyll-a. The models/ algorithms were calibrated/validated with field data collected in 2009, based on in situ radiometric (remote sensing reflectance -Rrs-) and limnological (chlorophyll-a concentrations - chl-a-) measurements. The chl-a concentrations were estimated by developing a semi-empirical band ratio (Rrs(708)/Rrs (664)) equation applied to MERIS images after correction for atmospheric effects with the 6S code. Results from this study suggest elevated spatial and temporal variability of chl-a. Spatial variability probably arises from the mosaic of situations within the Curonian lagoon in terms of bottom sediment features, nutrient availability in the water column, water depth and hydrodynamics. Temporal variability is probably linked to complex and interplaying meteorological and environmental constraints such as the length of the ice cover period, average water temperatures, wind-induced sediment resuspension, the pattern of precipitations and river-associated nutrient transport to the lagoon. This study stresses the importance of remote sensing as a valid tool for long-term whole ecosystem studies. The preliminary results need more through analyses and intersection with other environmental data in order to better comprehend algal bloom determinants in complex and extremely dynamic systems such as coastal lagoons.

Keywords: Remote sensing . MERIS . Chlorophyll-a . Eutrophication

Paper #6**Analysis of within- and between-day chlorophyll-a dynamics in Mantua Superior Lake, with a continuous spectroradiometric measurement**

Journal: *Marine and Freshwater Research*, 64, 303–316, 2013

Authors: M. Bresciani^{1,2}, M. Rossini³, G. Morabito⁴, E. Matta¹, M. Pinardi², S. Cogliati³, T. Julitta³, R. Colomb³, F. Braga⁵, C. Giardino¹

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Abstract: Shallow eutrophic lakes display unpredictable patterns of phytoplankton growth, distribution, vertical and horizontal migration, likely depending on environmental conditions. Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) monitoring provides reliable information on primary producer dynamics if monitored frequently. We present a practical approach which allows monitoring Chl-a in continuous with a radiometric system that measures water optical spectral properties. We tested this method in a shallow, nutrient rich lake in northern Italy, the Mantua Superior Lake, where the radiometric system collected data daily (i.e., every five-minutes), for about 30 days. Here, specifically developed algorithms were used to convert water reflectance to Chl-a concentration. The best performing algorithm ($R^2=0.863$) was applied to the larger dataset collected in September 2011. We characterized intra- and inter-daily Chl-a concentration dynamics and observed a high variability: in a single day Chl-a varied from 20 to 130 mg m⁻³. Chl-a concentration values were correlated to meteo-climatic parameters, showing that solar radiance and wind speed are key factors regulating the daily phytoplankton growth and dynamics. Such patterns are usually determined by vertical migration of different phytoplankton species within the water column as well as by metabolic adaptations to changes in light conditions.

Keywords: Water quality; optical properties; inland water systems; spectroradiometry; phytoplankton dynamics; meteorological factors

Running head: Monitoring Chl-a changes with spectroradiometric data

Paper #7**Assessing water quality in the northern Adriatic Sea from HICOTM data**

Journal: *Remote Sensing Letters*, Vol. 4, No. 10, 1028–1037, 2013

Authors: F. Braga¹, C. Giardino², C. Bassani³, E. Matta², G. Candiani², N. Strombeck⁴, M. Adamo⁵, M. Bresciani²

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Abstract: This letter focuses on water-quality estimation in the northern Adriatic Sea using physically-based methods applied to image obtained with the Hyperspectral Imager for the Coastal Ocean (HICOTM). Optical properties of atmosphere and water were synchronously measured to parameterise such methods. HICOTM-derived maps of chlorophyll-a (chl-a) and suspended particulate matter (SPM) indicated low values, in the range of 0–3 mg m⁻³ and 0–4 g m⁻³, respectively, correlating significantly with field data ($R^2 = 0.71$ for chl-a and $R^2 = 0.85$ for SPM). The results, on analysis, identify clear waters in the open sea and moderately turbid waters near the coast due to river sediment discharge and organic matter from coastal lagoons. These findings support the use of HICOTM data to assess water-quality parameters in coastal zones and suggest the feasibility of integrating them with future-generation space-borne hyperspectral images.

Keywords: Multi sensor, Chlorophyll-a concentration, Wind, ASAR, COSMO-Sky-MED, MERIS, MODIS

Paper #8**Multitemporal analysis of algal blooms with MERIS images in a deep meromictic lake**

Journal: *European Journal of Remote Sensing*, 46: 445-458, 2013

Authors: M. Bresciani^{1,2}, R. Bolpagni², Laini A.², Matta E.¹, Bartoli M.², Giardino C.¹

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Abstract: MERIS images (2003-2011) were used to detect algal bloom events in Lake Idro (Northern Italy) applying a semi-empirical algorithm. From the study of an intense phenomenon occurred in late summer 2010, a retrospective analysis of similar events during late summer/early autumn period was performed. High intra- and inter-annual variability was observed and three additional bloom events were identified on 2003, 2005 and 2008. Hydrological and weather parameters were examined at different temporal intervals (August-October, September-October and monthly from August to October) to investigate the regulating factors of bloom incidence. Rather low temperatures and the persistence of clouds seem to facilitate starting and maintenance of blooms

Keywords: Remote sensing, water quality, meteorological conditions, algal blooms, semi-empirical algorithm

Paper #9**On the synergistic use of SAR and optical imagery to monitor cyanobacteria blooms: the Curonian Lagoon case study**

Journal: *European Journal of Remote Sensing (in press)*, 2013

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Abstract: Multi-sensor satellite data are used to assess cyanobacteria blooms in the Curonian Lagoon. The exploitation of SAR images (COSMO-SkyMED, Envisat/ASAR), in combination with optical data (MERIS, MODIS), is investigated to take full advantage from the all-weather, night/day SAR imaging capability. A set of images acquired during 2011 and 2012 has been analyzed in order to: 1) study the effect of cyanobacteria on microwave signals; 2) assess the daily evolution of cyanobacteria bloom from multi-sensors data; and 3) evaluate the dependence of dynamics of blooms might have on winds. The results show a significant correlation ($R^2 > 0.8$, $p < 0.001$) between the X- and C-band Normalized Radar Cross Section (NRCS) attenuation and the NIR-Red band ratio Index, with the latter considered as a proxy for the presence of cyanobacteria blooms. A combined use of microwave and optical observations can improve the detection of cyanobacteria blooms and their dependency on wind action.

Keywords: Multi sensor, Chlorophyll-a concentration, Wind, ASAR, COSMO-Sky-MED, MERIS, MODIS

Paper #10**Feedback Mechanisms Between Cyanobacterial Blooms, Transient Hypoxia, and Benthic Phosphorus Regeneration in Shallow Coastal Environments****Journal:** *Estuaries and Coasts* (DOI 10.1007/s12237-013-9717-x), 2014**Authors:** M. Zilius¹, M. Bartoli², M. Bresciani^{2,3}, M. Katarzyte, T. Ruginis¹, J. Petkuvienė¹, I. Lubiene¹, C. Giardino³, P. A. Bukaveckas⁴, R. deWit^{1,5}, A. Razinkovas-Baziukas¹**Affiliation:** 1 Coastal Research and Planning Institute, Klaipėda University, 92294 Klaipėda, Lithuania; 2 Department of Environmental Sciences, Parma University, 43100 Parma, Italy; 3 Optical Remote Sensing Group, CNR-IREA, Via Bassini 15, 20133 Milano, Italy; 4 Department of Biology, Center for Environmental Studies, Virginia Commonwealth University, Richmond, VA 23284, USA; 5 Ecologie des Systèmes marins côtiers (Ecosym), UMR 5119, Université Montpellier 2, CNRS, IRD, Ifremer, Université Montpellier 1, Montpellier, France**Abstract:** We investigated the dissolved oxygen metabolism of the Curonian Lagoon (Baltic Sea) to assess the relative contributions of pelagic and benthic processes to the development of transient hypoxic conditions in shallow water habitats. Metabolism measurements along with the remote sensing-derived estimates of spatial variability in chlorophyll a were used to evaluate the risk of hypoxia at the whole lagoon level. Our data demonstrate that cyanobacterial blooms strongly inhibit light penetration, resulting in net heterotrophic conditions in which pelagic oxygen demand exceeds benthic oxygen demand by an order of magnitude. The combination of bloom conditions and reduced vertical mixing during calm periods resulted in oxygen depletion of bottom waters and greater sediment nutrient release. The peak of reactive P regeneration (nearly 30 $\mu\text{mol m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$) coincided with oxygen depletion in the water column, and resulted in a marked drop of the inorganic N:P ratio (from >40 to <5, as molar). Our results suggest a strong link between cyanobacterial blooms, pelagic respiration, hypoxia, and P regeneration, which acts as a feedback in sustaining algal blooms through internal nutrient cycling. Meteorological data and satellite-derived maps of chlorophyll a were used to show that nearly 70 % of the lagoon surface (approximately 1,000 km²) is prone to transient hypoxia development when blooms coincide with low wind speed conditions.**Paper #11****Observing blooms and surface accumulation of cyanobacteria in the Curonian Lagoon with combined use of MERIS and ASAR data****Journal:** *Remote Sensing of Environment* (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2013.07.040>), 2014**Authors:** M. Bresciani^{1,2}, M. P. Adamo³, G. De Carolis¹, E. Matta¹, G. Pasquariello³, D. Vaičiūtė⁴, C. Giardino¹**Affiliation:** 1 Optical Remote Sensing Group, CNR-IREA, Via Bassini 15, 20133 Milano, Italy; 2 University of Parma, Environmental Science Department, Viale Usberti 11/A, 43100 Parma, Italy; 3 Institute of Intelligent System Automatic, CNR-ISSIA, Via Amendola 122/D-O, 70126 Bari, Italy; 4 Coastal Research and Planning Institute, Klaipėda University, Herkaus Manto str. 84, LT-92294 Klaipėda, Lithuania**Abstract:** This study shows how different remote sensing techniques can be used to distinguish between surface accumulations (scum) and dense blooms of cyanobacteria in the Curonian Lagoon, the largest lagoon in Europe. Cyanobacteria blooms are a major concern in this region due to water quality issues interfering with the conservation of the whole ecosystem. Chlorophyll-a (Chl-a) concentrations can be extremely high (up to about 500 mg/m³ in some cases) during cyanobacteria blooms, which are often associated with a surface accumulation of algae. The Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MERIS) was used to acquire 52 images covering the summers of 2004 to 2011. These images were analyzed to map Chl-a concentrations and the presence of scum using two different band ratio algorithms applied to atmospherically-corrected data. The results identify wind speed as the main driving factor in the surface accumulation of algae, as well as in the spatial distribution of Chl-a. The utility of microwave images was also assessed, as since any cloud cover obviously hampers the use of optical data. Advanced Synthetic

Aperture Radar (ASAR) images were collected synchronously with the MERIS data and the normalized radar cross-section (NRCS) signal was corrected for the contribution of wind for the purposes of correlating the results with the MERIS-derived Chl-a concentrations. In general, there was a stepwise decrease in the NRCS for high values of Chl-a ($N50 \text{ mg/m}^3$) with wind speeds in the range of 2 to 6 m/s. Under these conditions, our results demonstrate that optical and microwave signals can be used in combination to improve our understanding of cyanobacteria blooming.

Keywords: MERIS, ASAR, Cyanobacteria, Scum, Chlorophyll-a, Water quality, Multi-sensor integration

Highlights: 1. Integration of MERIS and ASAR data to assess cyanobacteria blooms and scum. 2. Wind speed dependence of ASAR NRCS on Chl-a concentrations in the range 2-6 m/s. 3. Multi-temporal analysis to derive surface scum frequency maps.

Paper #12

Optical Remote Sensing of lakes: An Overview on Lake Maggiore

Journal: *Journal of limnology (in press)*, 2014

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Abstract: Optical satellite remote sensing represents an opportunity to integrate traditional methods for assessing water quality of lakes: strengths of remote sensing methods are the good spatial and temporal coverage, the possibility to monitor many lakes simultaneously and the reduced costs. Suspended particulate matter (SPM), algal bloom, chlorophyll-a (chl-a) and accessory pigments, coloured dissolved organic matter (CDOM), and surface temperature are the most common parameters which can be inferred from Earth Observation (EO) data. Moreover, remote sensing techniques have been proved to be a suitable tool for producing both maps of bathymetry and bottom properties and of substances which are floating on the water's surface (e.g., scum, floating vegetation). In this work we present an overview of optical remote sensing techniques applied to lake water monitoring. Then, examples of applications focused on Lake Maggiore, the second largest lake in Italy are discussed, by presenting the temporal trend of chl-a, SPM, CDOM and the z90 signal depth (the latter indicating the water depth from which 90% of the reflected light comes from) as estimated from the images acquired by the Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrometer (MERIS) in the pelagic area of the lake from 2003 to 2011. Concerning the chl-a trend, the results are in agreement with the concentration values measured during field surveys, confirming the good status of Lake Maggiore, although salutary events of water deterioration were observed (e.g., an average increase of chl-a concentration, with a decrease of transparency, as a consequence of an anomalous phytoplankton occurred in summer 2011). A series of MERIS-derived maps (summer period 2011) of the z90 signal are also analysed in order to show the spatial variability of lake waters, which on average were clearer in the central pelagic zones. We expect that the recently launched (e.g., Landsat-8) and the future satellite missions (e.g., Sentinel-3) carrying sensors with improved spectral and spatial resolution are going to lead to a larger use of remote sensing for the assessment and monitoring of water quality parameters, by also allowing further applications (e.g., classification of phytoplankton functional types) to be developed.

Keywords: Earth Observation, MERIS, water quality, surface temperature

Paper #13

The use of ocean colour remote sensing in integrated coastal zone management- a case study from Himmerfjärden, Sweden.

Journal: *Marine Policy* **43**, 29–39; 2014, published on-line 22 May 2013.

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Abstract: In this study the use of ocean color data as a diagnostic tool in integrated coastal zone management was investigated as part of the Science Policy Integration for Coastal Systems Assessment (SPICOSA) project. Parallel to this, an operational coastal monitoring system has been set up in close collaboration with endusers. The core work of the bio-optical part in the project was to develop Secchi depth and attenuation of light as indicators for coastal zone management, by linking remote sensing with the socio-economic and ecological model developed in SPICOSA. The article emphasizes the benefits of stakeholder involvement and end-user feedback for efficient and improved system development. Furthermore, conceptual models were developed on how to integrate remote sensing data into coastal zone management and into a physical-biological model of the Baltic Sea. One of the work packages in the SPICOSA project was academic training. In this work package, on-line teaching material in the field of remote sensing and biooptics was developed and disseminated on the SETnet web page. The article presented here may act as supportive material for training in bio-optics and remote sensing.

Paper #14

Remote sensing of phytoplankton-macrophyte coexistence in shallow hypereutrophic fluvial lakes

Journal: *Hydrobiologia* (in press)

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Abstract: We investigated with remote sensing (APEX images) the coexistence of phytoplankton and macrophytes in three interconnected shallow and hypereutrophic fluvial lakes (Mantua Lakes, Northern Italy). High concentrations of chlorophyll-a, up to 60 mg m⁻³, were determined in the open water between well-developed stands of floating-leaved, submerged and emergent macrophyte stands. Our data suggest a general inhibition of phytoplankton by macrophytes, evidenced by decreasing chlorophyll-a concentrations in proximity of macrophyte stands. Chlorophyll-a concentrations halved in the proximity of emergent stands (~6 mg m⁻³ within 21 m from the stand border) when compared to the outer zones (~13 mg m⁻³). Contrasting trends were observed for submerged stands, where concentrations decreased inwards from ~8 to ~3 mg m⁻³. Floating leaved stands had a neutral effect, chlorophyll-a being nearly constant in both inner and outer zones. Overall, remotely-sensed data allow to evaluate quantitative and spatially defined interactions of macrophytes and phytoplankton at the whole ecosystem scale.

Keywords: Fluvial lakes; Airborne data; APEX images; Macrophyte growth forms; Phytoplankton

Paper #15**Satellite-based water quality monitoring for improved spatial and temporal retrieval of chlorophyll-a in coastal waters**

Journal: *Remote Sensing Environment* (resubmitted with changes)

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Abstract: The coastal zones are the most inhabited areas of the world and are therefore strongly affected by humans, leading to undesirable environmental changes that may alter the ecosystems, such as eutrophication. In order to evaluate changes in the environment an effective water quality monitoring system for the coastal zones must be in place. The chlorophyll-a concentration is commonly used as a proxy for phytoplankton biomass and as indicator for eutrophication and it can be retrieved from ocean colour remote sensing data. Several operational monitoring systems based on remote sensing are in place to monitor the open sea and, to some extent, the coastal zones. However, evaluations of coastal monitoring systems based on satellite data are scarce. This paper compares the chlorophyll-a concentrations retrieved from an operational satellite system based on MERIS (Medium Resolution Imaging Spectrophotometer) data with ship-based monitoring for the productive seasons in 2008 and 2010, in a coastal area in the Baltic Sea. The comparisons showed that the satellite-based monitoring system is reliable and that the estimations of chlorophyll-a concentration is comparable to in situ measurements in terms of accuracy and quantitative retrieval. A very strong correlation was found between measurements from satellite-derived chlorophyll-a compared to in situ measurements taken close in time (0-3 days). The comparison of the monthly means also showed a significant correlation. Furthermore, this study shows that MERIS is better at capturing spatial dynamics and the extent of phytoplankton blooms than ship-based monitoring, since it has a synoptic view and higher temporal resolution. Satellite-based monitoring also increases the frequency of chlorophyll-a observations considerably, where the degree of improvement is dependent on the sampling frequency of the respective monitoring program. Our results show that ocean colour remote sensing can, when combined with field sampling, provide an improved basis for more effective monitoring and management of the coastal zone. These results are important for eutrophication assessment and status classifications of water basins and can be applied to a larger extent within national and international agreements considering the coastal zones, e.g. the European Commission's Water Framework Directive.

Paper #16**Wavelet enhanced semi-analytical inversion of apex imagery for water quality estimation of the Mantua lake, Italy**

Journal: *Remote Sensing* (in review)

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This paper presents an application of continuous wavelet analysis, providing a novel semi-analytical inversion model to estimate chlorophyll (CHL), total suspended matter (TSM) and colored dissolved organic matter (CDOM) from high spectral resolution data of optically complex waters. Complex waters are challenging due to the complex optical mixture of the constituents. Also, model inversion is often impeded by noise and confounding factors. Therefore, there is a need for robust and flexible model inversion techniques. We propose WAVE-SIM, a wavelet enhanced semi-analytical inversion model, which uses wavelet transformed reflectance spectra in a predictor-corrector optimization scheme. Since WAVE-SIM has been developed on simulated spectra this paper is a first *in situ* application, this to airborne APEX (Airborne Prism Experiment) imagery of Mantua Lake, Italy. WAVE-SIM outperformed a well published model as it is able to

decouple the combined and interaction influence of the confounding factors and it is less sensitive to noise. It could therefore produce reliable APEX water quality products for CHL, TSM and CDOM. Future research should extend this framework to other applications and apply it to spaceborne remote sensing data.

6 Conclusions

The project has reached all the aims established, The results obtained have highlighted the relevance of using of remote sensing techniques for the study of water quality, for understanding of the phenomena of cyanobacteria bloom.

Through the project, it was possible share scientific and technological knowledge in the field measuraments and in the image processing; perform education activates towards MsSc. and PhD students and published many scientific papers.

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